

VITAMIN D DEFICIENCY AND RICKETS IN CHILDREN IN CENTRAL ROMANIA**Drd. Antonescu Irina Elena***County Emergency Hospital Sibiu, Romania***Drd. Antonescu Oana Raluca***Lucian Blaga University of Sibiu, Faculty of Medicine, Surgical Clinical Department, Romania***Dr. Totan Maria***Lucian Blaga University of Sibiu, Faculty of Medicine, Preclinical Department, Romania*<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13134465>**Abstract**

In recent years, medical literature has extensively studied the association between vitamin D concentration and various pathologies. Dietary intake, inadequate utilization of vitamin D, and insufficient exposure to sunlight lead to vitamin D deficiency and rickets in children and adolescents. Vitamin D plays an important role in calcium absorption and in maintaining healthy bones.

The aim of this study is to analyze 25(OH)D deficiency in children up to 18 months of age with a presumptive diagnosis of rickets.

A retrospective study was conducted, which included 162 children aged up to 18 months, hospitalized between January 2020 and January 2023 at the Clinical Pediatric Hospital in Sibiu. It has been observed that in our geographical area, there is a significant number of children with suboptimal vitamin D levels and a high percentage of cases diagnosed with rickets (48.7%).

Keywords: vitamin D deficiency, rickets, children

Introduction

Vitamin D deficiency is common in many developing countries and is considered to be the main cause of nutritional rickets (1,2). Vitamin D interferes with the absorption of calcium, which is an important element for the body because of its functions in bone mineralization, bone formation and maintenance of bone structure and rigidity (3,4,5). Vitamin D deficiency is also due to malabsorption of vitamin D and calcium (6). Iron is also considered an essential nutrient, the adult body contains 3-4 g of iron (7) which, together with vitamin D, contributes to normal growth and development of the child, deficiency of one of the parameters leading to deficiency of the other, these elements being essential in maintaining normal cell function (8).

Vitamin D deficiency is widespread in individuals irrespective of age, sex, race and geographical area (9). Low levels of 25(OH)D have been associated with cognitive impairment in dementia (10), depressive symptoms (11) and aggressive behavior in young people (12).

Vitamin D deficiency is a major health concern and it is difficult to determine what adequate exposure of an individual's skin to sunlight is (6). The amount of vitamin D synthesized by UV exposure depends on many factors other than time spent outdoors, such as: season, amount of exposed skin, degree of skin pigmentation, latitude, body mass, degree of air pollution, clothing and sunscreens used (13).

For photosynthesis of vitamin D in optimal concentrations, a total body exposure time of 10-15 minutes/day is sufficient during the summer months for an individual with mild pigmentation.

Darker skin has a high content of melanin which acts as a natural sunscreen, so in darker-skinned people much less vitamin D is produced and more exposure is

needed to generate similar amounts of vitamin D (6,9,14).

This level would be sufficient for most known effects of vitamin D, but also to avoid problems regarding vitamin toxicity [9].

Vitamin D deficiency is defined as serum levels of 25(OH)D <20 ng/mL. Vitamin D is considered insufficient if serum 25(OH)D levels are between (20-29) ng/mL. If serum 25(OH)D levels are 30 ng/mL, intestinal calcium absorption is maximal and parathyroid hormone (PTH) levels continue to fall until this 25(OH)D level is reached (15). Thus, the optimal and safe serum 25(OH)D level is defined as between (30-100) ng/mL (3,16).

Deficiency of vitamin D occurs gradually. In the first step, the 25-OH-D level decreases and the levels of calcium in many cases decrease resulting in hypocalcemia, but optimal levels of calcium are also met. In stage II, the 25-OH-D level decreases further; PTH hormone enters into action to preserve calcium through bone demineralization; the levels of calcium remain normal, phosphatemia is low and the alkaline phosphatase level is slightly increased.

In stage III, severe deficiency of 25-OH-D is established with increased hypocalcaemia, hypophosphatemia and alkaline phosphatase; the bones have obvious signs of demineralization [6,17]

No longer considered a disease of the past or a disease of low-income countries, rickets is a nutritional disease caused by hypovitaminosis D, characterized by a maturation deficiency of bone matrix protein. The disease occurs during growth, leading to a disturbance in phospho-focalcic metabolism (18), with children in the first 18 months of life being most affected (19).

Vitamin D deficiency leads to delay in closure of infant fontanelle, dental retardation, muscular hypotonia, pallor, irritability [2].

Many clinical studies have shown that vitamin D deficiency can lead to infectious diseases, cardiovascular [20,21] and respiratory diseases [20], autoimmune diseases [21,22,23], depression, diabetes, and cancer [22,23].

The aim of the study is to identify the vitamin D concentration in children up to 18 months of age in the county of Sibiu who had a presumptive diagnosis of rickets.

Materials and method

A retrospective study was conducted, which included 162 children aged up to 18 months, hospitalized between January 2020 and January 2023 at the Clinical Pediatric Hospital of Sibiu, which is located in central Romania. Patients in the study group were divided into three groups: < 6 months, 6 - 12 months and 12 - 18 months (Table 1).

Table 1.

Demographic characteristics of patients

Demographic characteristics	Age			Gen		Geographical area	
	<6 months	(6-12) months	(12-18) months	F	M	Rural	Urban
N	31	47	84	66	96	58	104
%	19.13	29.01	51.87	40.74	59.26	35.80	64.20

Values for 25(OH)D concentration were taken from the electronic archive of the Medical Laboratory.

The 25(OH)D assay was performed from serum on the Vidas analyzer using the ELFA method. The reagents used were from BioMerieux, France. This enzyme immunoassay utilizes a competitive assay principle using recombinant vitamin D binding protein.

All blood samples were collected by venipuncture in a vacutainer without anticoagulant, with/without separating gel. Collected blood was left at room temperature for at least 30 minutes, then centrifuged at 3000 rpm for 10 minutes.

The criteria for the inclusion of patients in this study were: maximum age of 18 months and presence

of clinical signs of rickets. Exclusion criteria were as follows: refusal to participate in the study, a diagnosis that did not meet the guidelines of the Diagnostic Guidelines, or the presence of any concomitant acute or chronic disease other than rickets.

Statistical processing. Statistics were performed with the program GraphPad vers.9, data normality was achieved using the Shapiro-Wilk test (27). The significance threshold for all tests was 0.05.

Results

38.7% of children were 25(OH)D deficient, 40.4% of children had 25(OH)D insufficiency, and only 20.9% of the patients included in the study had an optimum level of 25(OH)D (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Distribution of patients according to serum 25(OH)D levels

In patients <6 months of age, there was a 25(OH)D deficiency of 5.2%, a 25(OH)D insufficiency of 38.4% and an optimal 25(OH)D level of 56.4%. The highest deficiency of 25(OH)D was observed in patients aged 6-12 months (22.4%), which was significant (25(OH)D concentration < 20 ng/ml, with a mean of (8.60 ± 1.10) ng/ml). Also, this age group showed a high insufficiency of this vitamin (32.1% of patients), with 25(OH)D levels ranging from 21-30 ng/ml (mean value

(21.5 ± 1.7) ng/ml).

In the 12-18 months age group, the 25(OH)D deficiency was 11.1%, a small percentage showed an optimal 25(OH)D level (5.1% of patients), with the highest 25(OH)D insufficiency (83.8%) (Figure 2).

In terms of 25(OH)D insufficiency, there were no statistically significant differences (p = 0.062) between the 6-12 months age group and children <6 months.

Figure 2. Distribution of 25(OH)D level by age group

The patients studied showed various clinical signs of rickets (Table 2).

parietal bossing, parieto-occipital plagiocephaly, bell-shaped thorax, muscle hypotonia.

The most suggestive clinical signs in patients with rickets were: wide-open anteriorfontanelle, frontal and

Table 2.

Suggestive clinical signs of patients included in the study

Types of clinical signs for vitamin D deficiency	Description of clinical signs
Type A	widely opened anteriorfontanelle, frontal and parietal bossing, parieto – occipital plagiocephaly,craniotabes
Type B	bell-shaped thorax
Type C	muscular hypotonia

Figure 3. Suggestive clinical signs by age groups

48% of patients < 6 months of age showed clinical signs suggestive of common nutritional rickets: wide open anterior fontanelle, frontal and parietal bossing, parieto-occipital plagiocephaly, craniotabes.

In the 6-12 months age group, 68% showed suggestive signs such as wide open anterior fontanelle, frontal and parietal prominence, parieto-occipital plagiocephaly, craniotabes, 51% of patients showed signs of bell-shaped thorax and 42% showed signs of muscle hypotonia.

38% of patients presented with signs of bell-shaped thorax and 28% of patients presented with the clinical picture of nutritional rickets shared with other signs, including muscle hypotonia.

In the age group 12-18 months, 81% of patients showed suggestive signs such as wide open anterior

fontanelle, frontal and parietal bossing, parieto-occipital plagiocephaly, craniotabes, 72% of patients showed signs of bell-shaped thorax and 56% of patients showed signs of muscle hypotonia.

Discussions

During periods of growth, vitamin D deficiency can have a negative influence on bone development, interfering with normal growth and development and causing rickets in the most severe cases.

Vitamin D deficiency is common among children and rickets has become a global health problem. In addition to vitamin D deficiency, calcium deficiency is also involved in rickets. Calcium and vitamin D deficiency can compromise children's growth and development (3). The increasing percentage of suggestive clinical signs in the age group 12-18 months suggests the onset and progression of signs of rickets with increasing age.

The onset of the disease usually begins at 3-4 months of age. The highest incidence has been recorded in the 6-18 months age group, consistent with the literature (28).

A study conducted in Bucharest, Romania, identified a prevalence of vitamin D deficiency in children of 61.6%, with 6.2% of patients having severe vitamin D deficiency and 55.4% having moderate vitamin D deficiency (29).

A study of asthma patients in Cluj Napoca, Romania, found that the prevalence of suboptimal 25(OH)D was 58.8% (30).

It can be noted that the prevalence of vitamin D deficiency obtained in a 2017 study was 42.5%, a deficiency that was found in patients living in urban areas (31,32).

At this age, children experience rapid growth, requiring greater amounts of calcium and phosphorus to strengthen and develop the skeletal system. In children whose mothers have hypovitaminosis, the disease may occur earlier (3). To eradicate rickets in infants and children, exposure to sunlight, an economical method or vitamin D supplementation is needed (9,33).

Calcium, phosphorus, iron, together with vitamin D, play an important role in children's health, growth and development.

In rickets, serum levels of vitamin D, calcium and phosphorus are low in many cases, while serum levels of alkaline phosphatase are usually elevated

Various commercial vitamin D preparations are used to correct vitamin D deficiency. It is difficult to accurately determine the recommended dose of vitamin D because it is produced endogenously and stored for long periods of time in adipose tissues. The body's requirement depends on skin pigmentation and sun exposure, dietary intake of calcium and phosphorus, age, sex (2,3).

To avoid vitamin D deficiency, a vitamin D dose of 400 IU/day is recommended for all infants, children and adolescents (5,6).

Vitamin D deficiency, and not only vitamin D deficiency, can also occur if patients lack the knowledge or are unwilling to identify vitamin-rich foods (25,26).

A way of understanding for all researchers studying this problem, the solution would be a formalization, but also the realization of predictive models (34,35,36) that can rapidly identify vitamin D deficiency and particularly rickets.

Conclusions

Determination of 25(OH)D levels and parameters involved in the diagnosis of rickets is useful in children up to 18 months of age for the preventive treatment of rickets to be instituted at this age.

High vitamin D deficiency raises red flags and alerts for pediatric healthcare, necessitating a prophylactic vitamin D program for rickets in children. Poor medical education for rural families, as well as dermatologists' recommendations to protect children's skin from UV radiation by using cosmetics with a protective factor, also lead to vitamin D deficiency and rickets over time.

References:

1. Munns CF, Shaw N, Kiely M, Specker BL, Thacher TD, Thacher TD, Ozone K, Högl W. Global consensus recommendations on the prevention and management of nutritional rickets. *Hormone Research in Pediatrics*. 2016; 85(2), 83-106.
2. Thandrayen K, Pettifor JM. Roles of vitamin D and dietary calcium in nutritional rickets. *Bone Reports*. 2018; 8, 81-89.
3. Edouard T, Linglart A, Salles JP. Vitamin D and rickets: debates, consensus and practical use. *Perfectionnement en Pédiatrie*. 2018; 1(1), 40-47.
4. Wimalawansa SJ, Razzaque MS, Al-Daghri NM. Calcium and vitamin D in human health: hype or real. *Journal of steroid biochemistry and molecular biology*. 2018; 180, 4- 14.
5. Creo AL, Thacher TD, Pettifor JM, Strand MA, Fischer PR. Nutritional rickets worldwide: an update. *Pediatrics and International Child Health*. 2017; 37(2), 84-98.
6. Christakos S, Veldurthy V, Patel N, Wei R. Intestinal calcium regulation: vitamin D and bone physiology. *Understanding the gut-bone signaling axis*. 2017; 3-12.
7. Totan M, Antonescu E, Gligor FG. Quantitative spectrophotometric determinations of Fe³⁺ in iron polymaltose solution. *Indian Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences*. 2018; 80(2), 268-273.
8. Liu C, Li X, Zhao Z, Chi Y, Chi Y, Cui L, Zhang Q, Xia W. Iron deficiency plays essential roles in the onset, treatment and prognosis of autosomal dominant hypophosphatemic autosomal dominant rickets. *Osteoporosis international*. 2020; 1-9.
9. Gupta A. Vitamin D deficiency in India: prevalence, causation and interventions. *Nutrients*. 2014; 6(2), 729-775.
10. Moretti R, Caruso P, Dal Ben M, Conti C, Gazzin S, Tiribelli C. Vitamin D, homocysteine and folate in subcortical vascular dementia and Alzheimer's dementia. *Frontiers in the neuroscience of aging*. 2017; 9, 169.
11. Parker GB, Brotchie H, Graham RK. Vitamin D and depression. *Journal of affective disorders*. 2017;

208, 56-61.

12. Patrick RP, Ames BN. Vitamin D and omega-3 fatty acids control serotonin synthesis and action, part 2: Relevance to ADHD, bipolar disorder, schizophrenia, and impulsive behavior. *The FASEB Journal*. 2015; 29(6), 2207-2222.

13. Coussens AK. Role of UV radiation and vitamin D in seasonality and infectious disease outcomes. *Photochemical and photobiological sciences*. 2017; 16(3), 314-338.

14. Kagotho E, Omuse G, Okinda N, Ojwang P. Vitamin D status in healthy black African adults at a tertiary hospital in Nairobi, Kenya: a cross-sectional study. *BMC Endocrine Disorders*. 2018; 18(1), 1-7.

15. Sabir MS, Haussler MR, Mallick S, Kaneko I, Lucas DA, Haussler CA, Jurutka PW. Optimal vitamin D stimulates serotonin: 1, 25-dihydroxyvitamin D represses serotonin reuptake transporter (SERT) and degradation (MAO-A) gene expression in cultured rat serotonergic neuronal serotonergic neuronal cell lines. *Genes and Nutrition*. 2018; 13(1), 1-11.

16. Yang A, Lv Q, Chen F, Wang D, Liu Y, Shi W. Identifying recent trends in vitamin D research: a quantitative and co-word analysis. *Medical science monitor: international medical journal of experimental and clinical research*. 2019; 25, 643

17. Carpenter TO, Shaw NJ, Portale AA, Ward LM, Abrams SA, Pettifor JM. Rickets. *Nature Reviews Disease Primers*. 2017; 3(1), 1-20.

18. Chibuzor MT, Graham-Kalio D, Osaji JO, Meremikwu MM. Vitamin D, calcium or a combination of vitamin D and calcium for the treatment of nutritional rickets in children. *Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews*. 2020; (4)

19. El Kholly M, Elsedfy H, Fernández-Cancio M, Hamza RT, Amr NH, Ahmed AY, Audí L. Nutritional rickets: vitamin D, calcium and genetic composition. *Pediatric Research*. 2017; 81(2), 356-363

20. Valer-Martinez A, Martinez JA, Sayon-Orea C, Galvano F, Grosso G, Bes-Rastrollo M. Vitamin D and cardio-metabolic risk factors in overweight adults: an overview of the evidence. *Current Pharmaceutical Design*. 2019; 25(22), 2407-2420.

21. Zhou J, Du J, Huang L, Wang Y, Shi Y, Lin H. Preventive effects of vitamin D on seasonal influenza A in infants: a multicenter, randomized, open-label, open-label, controlled, multicenter clinical trial. *Journal of Pediatric Infectious Diseases*. 2018; 37(8), 749-754.

22. Del Giudice MM, Indolfi C, Strisciuglio C. Vitamin D: immunomodulatory aspects. *Journal of clinical gastroenterology*. 2018; 52, S86-S88.

23. Skrobot A, Demkow U, Wachowska M. Immunomodulatory role of vitamin D: a review. *Current trends in immunity and respiratory infections*. 2018; 13-23.

24. Mondul AM, Weinstein SJ, Layne TM, Albanes D. Vitamin D and cancer risk and mortality: state

of the science, gaps, and challenges. *Epidemiologic Reviews*. 2017; 39(1), 28-48.

25. Avram C, Avram L, Ruta F, Georgescu IM, Rus V. Consumer profile of food label reading in Mures county, Romania- a pilot study: Consumer profile of food label reading in Mures county, Romania. *Progr Nutr*. 2021;22(4):e2020072.

26. Antonescu E, Bota G, Serb B, Atasiu D, Dahm Tataru C, Totan M et al. Study of the total serum concentration of serum ionized magnesium in children and adolescents from Sibiu Area. *Rev. Chem*. 2018; 69(12), 3389-3392.

27. Avram C, Mărușteri M. Assessment of normality, some paradigms and use cases. *Rev Romana Med Lab*. 2022;30(3):251-9.

28. Siafarikas A, Simm P, Zacharin M, Jefferies C, Lafferty AR, Wheeler BJ, APEG Bone and Mineral Working Group. Global consensus on nutritional rickets: implications for Australia. *Journal of Pediatrics and Child Health*. 2020; 56(6), 841-846.

29. Stan IV, Bălănescu A, Codreanu IF, Belivaca AA, Ritivoiu ME, Drăgoi MM, Marinescu SA, Ali C, Comănici VD. Vitamin D 125(OH) deficiency in children with cystic fibrosis, a prospective study on prevalence and treatment outcome. *Farmacia*. 2019; 67(3), 423-429

30. Adam-Bonci TI, Cherecheș-Panța P, Bonci EA, Man SC, Cutaș-Benedec A, Drugan T, Pop RM, Irimie A. Suboptimal Serum 25-Hydroxy-Vitamin D Is Associated with a History of Recent Disease Exacerbation in Pediatric Patients with Bronchial Asthma or Asthma-Suggestive Recurrent Recurrent Wheezing. *Int J Environ Res Public Health*. 2020; 17(18),6545.

31. Totan M, Antonescu E, Rus L, Grigore N, Gligor F. Prevalence of vitamin D deficiency in children. *Proceedings of the National Congress of Pharmacy of Romania, 17th edition*. 2018; 228-233.

32. Voda M, Murgu A, Sarpe CA, Graves SM, Avram C. Gypsy community adaptability to changes in rural Romania and the impact of COVID-19. *Int. J. Environ. Res. Public Health* 2021, 18, 10622.

33. Antonescu OR, Silișteanu AE, Racheriu M, Mihalache, C. Assessment of the importance of physical activity and quality of life for patients diagnosed with osteoporosis during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Balneo and PRM Research Journal*. 2021; 12(4), 386-391

34. Călin A, Adrian G, Laura AE (2012). New approach on optimal decision making based on formal automatic models. *Procedia Economics and Finance* 2012;3,852-857.

35. Călin A, Laura AE, Adrian G. (2014) Formal models for mathematical programming problem description. *Procedia Economics and Finance* 2014;15,1501-1506.

36. Călin A, Adrian G, Laura AE (2020) Automated decision making based on formal models. *Procedia Manufacturing* 2020, 46; 573-579.